

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

THE EFFECT OF VOLCANIC ASH ON THE PROPERTIES OF DRY CEMENT-BASED CONSTRUCTION MIXTURES

Xalilov Y.,

PhD in Engineering, Associate Professor of the Design Department of Baku Engineering University

Akbarova S.,

PhD in Engineering, Associate Professor of the Materials Science Department of Azerbaijan Architecture and Construction University

Shahmarov V.

PhD in Engineering, Associate Professor of the Materials Science Department of Azerbaijan Architecture and Construction University

ABSTRACT

This study examines the effect of volcanic ash (VA) on the physical, mechanical, rheological, and functional properties of cement-based dry construction mixtures (DCM). As a result of X-ray phase analysis (XPA) and chemical analysis (XRF), the composition of VA was found to contain 78% amorphous glass phase, 11% quartz and 9% feldspar, and its pozzolan activity was 79 mg CaO/g. As a result of replacing quartz sand with VA in proportions of 5%, 10%, 15% and 20%, the optimal range was found to be 10–15%, which allowed the amount of free calcium oxide to be reduced from 5.2% to 1.4%. This confirms the intense reaction of pozzolan. The presence of VA in the composition increases the setting time of the mortar from 8 to 12 hours, its plasticity and adhesive strength, but reduces the density from 1800 kg/m³ to 1760 kg/m³. After 28 days of hardening, the compressive strength of compositions with 15% VA approaches the control sample (16.5 MPa) and is 15.6 MPa. The most important result was that VA increased the sorption moisture content from 1.8% to 4.2%. This indicates the material's potential for regulating moisture balance in high-humidity environments (basements, bathrooms). The results confirm the promise of Mollada VA for the production of a new generation of high-moisture, environmentally friendly and high-performance DCM.

Keywords: volcanic ash, pozzolanic activity, dry construction mixture, sorption moisture, adhesion, cement, ecological material.

1. INTRODUCTION

In recent decades, rapid developments in materials science in the construction industry, particularly the search for energy-efficient, environmentally friendly and functional compositions, have led to a re-evaluation of active minerals of natural origin. In this regard, additives containing pozzolan, including volcanic ash, are becoming an important alternative to cement systems from both a technological and environmental point of view (Hossain, 2003; Rosales et al., 2022). The high amorphousness, fine dispersion and high silica content of volcanic minerals allow them to enter into synergistic reactions with cement, increasing hydration kinetics and durability.

Dry construction mixtures (DCM) are one of the most dynamically developing classes of materials in modern construction. Their advantage lies in the fact that the binding component and active functional additives are combined in optimised proportions under laboratory conditions, ensuring stable particle size distribution and rheological stability. This simplifies not only the production technology, but also the application at the site, improving the quality and environmental safety of the product (Dergunov and Orekhov, 2005; Bazhenov, 2011; Korneev et al., 2022).

However, due to the chemical and technological similarity of numerous products available on the market, the number of mixtures that fully meet aesthetic, sanitary, hygienic and functional requirements remains limited. Traditional solutions used in rooms with high humidity, such as bathrooms, basements, attics and

kitchens, face problems such as the development of fungal and bacterial colonies, surface deformation and a reduction in aesthetic qualities (Nikolaenko, 2014; Larsen et al., 2020). In this regard, the development of new-generation mixtures that remain stable in humid conditions and have antibacterial potential is a pressing issue.

Due to its pozzolanic activity, natural volcanic ash not only increases the mechanical strength of cement systems, but also provides excellent properties such as water resistance and salt tolerance, the ability to regulate humidity and neutralise calcium hydroxide in the air (Hossain, 2005; Frías et al., 2005). Volcanic ash reacts with free CaO released during Portland cement hydration, altering the phase composition of CSH and CAH hydration products, resulting in a denser structure and long-term stability (Berry & Malhotra, 1980; De Rojas & Frías, 1996).

The availability of large reserves of highly active volcanic ash in a number of countries around the world, including Azerbaijan, indicates the broad potential of the raw material base for dry construction mixtures in this area. Scientific research into these materials and their use in cement-based dry construction mixtures is of strategic importance both in terms of expanding the raw material base and developing sustainable construction technologies. Previous studies have shown that Jeyranchola volcanic ash has high reactivity due to its 70–75% amorphous glass phase content, and its use in cement systems in amounts of 10–15% gives optimal results (Khalilov et al., 2024).

The aim of this study is to experimentally investigate the effect of Moladag volcanic ash (Azerbaijan, Tovuz district) on the physical, mechanical and hygienic properties of dry cement-based building mixtures and to assess its practical application. The scientific novelty of the work lies in the fact that volcanic ash was evaluated not only as an additive that increases mechanical strength, but also as an active component that optimises sorption moisture and improves adhesion to the surface. The results show that this approach is an effective example of an environmentally friendly approach based on local resources for creating a new generation of dry building materials.

Experimental methodology

In the first stage of the study, the pozzolanic activity of volcanic ash (VA) was determined. Determining activity is a key factor in quantitatively assessing the reactivity of the additive and its potential to bind free

calcium hydroxide [Ca(OH)₂] in the cement matrix. For this purpose, a standardised method was used – the lime absorption method (GOST 25094, 2018). As a result of the experiments, the activity of Molladag VA was 79 mg CaO/g, which indicates that it belongs to the medium activity category and can be effectively used in cement systems.

A Bruker S8 TIGER (Germany) energy-dispersive X-ray fluorescence (EDX) spectrometer was used to analyse the chemical composition of the materials. The results are presented in Table 1. To determine the mineralogical phase composition of volcanic ash, in particular the amount of amorphous (glass-like) phase, which is the main source of pozzolanic activity, a Rigaku Miniflex 600 X-ray diffractometer (Japan) was used. The diffractometer operated with a copper anode (CuK α radiation), and the resulting diffractogram is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Diffractogram of volcanic ash

Table 1.

Mineralogical composition of volcanic ash

Molladag volcanic ash	Mineralogical composition of volcanic ash, mass. %				
	Quartz (SiO ₂)	Feldspar (NaAlSi ₃ O ₈)	Hematite (Fe ₂ O ₃)	Volcanic glass	Total
	11	9	2	78	100

Table 2.

Chemical composition of volcanic ash

Molladag volcanic ash	Chemical composition of volcanic ash, mass %							
	Na ₂ O	MgO	Al ₂ O ₃	SiO ₂	K ₂ O	CaO	FeO	C _{emi}
	3,45	1,25	14,20	72,45	4,24	1,33	3,08	100

Based on the results of chemical and X-ray phase analysis, a quantitative phase analysis was performed, the results of which are presented in Table 2. The analysis showed that the mineralogical composition of volcanic ash is mainly represented by glass phase (78%), feldspar (9%) and quartz (11%). Such a high content of the predominant amorphous glass phase is the direct cause of the high pozzolanic activity of the material and determines its hydraulic activity.

It is known that the optimal dosage of pozzolan additives in cement systems is directly determined by their activity. The use of large amounts of additives with relatively low activity can lead to a significant portion of them acting as ‘ballast’ without effectively participating in the formation of the structure, which is impractical (Larsen et al., 2020). Based on this, the experimental part of the study investigated the effect of systematic additives on the technological (rheological)

and mechanical properties of compositions prepared by replacing quartz sand with volcanic ash in certain proportions (5%, 10%, 15% and 20%).

Discussion of research results

1. Determination of the optimal amount of volcanic ash

One of the main objectives of the study was to determine the optimal ratio of volcanic ash (VA) replacement with quartz sand in dry building mixtures. To this end, a standard composition of a dry mixture based on Portland cement (40% Portland cement grade 42.5, 59% quartz sand, 1% polymer and cellulose additives) was taken as a basis, with 5%, 10%, 15% and 20% of quartz sand replaced with finely dispersed VA.

After 28 days of hydration of each composition, X-ray phase analysis (XPA) was performed to determine the content of free calcium oxide (CaO). The results showed that replacing VA in the range of 10–15% led to a sharp decrease in the content of free CaO (from

5.2% to 1.4%). This confirms that VA effectively enters into a pozzolanic reaction with free CaO released during cement hydration and converts it into additional hardening products (C-S-H phases).

However, when replacing up to 20%, no further decrease in the level of free CaO is observed. This indicates an insufficient amount of free CaO in the system for reaction with VA or a limitation of the reaction efficiency by the physical density of VA particles. In addition, when replacing up to 20%, the granulometric composition of the mixture is disturbed; with a significant reduction in the volume of filler (sand), the 'skeletal' structure is weakened, which can negatively affect the mechanical strength of the hardened mortar (the data in Tables 3 and 4 confirm this conclusion).

Thus, based on the analyses conducted, the optimal replacement amount for VA Molladag was determined to be in the range of 10–15%. In this range, the pozzolanic activity of VA is maximised, while the structural integrity of the mixture is maintained.

Table 3.

Technological properties of dry construction mixtures containing volcanic ash

Portland cement, %	Quartz sand, %	Volcanic ash, %	Normal density, %	Setting time, hour.		Plasticity, cm	Density of mortar, kg/m ³
				Start, min	The end, hour		
40	59	-	27	40	8	8	1800
40	54	5	29	42	9	8	1790
40	49	10	31	46	10	9	1780
40	44	15	32	50	11	9	1775
40	39	20	34	58	12	9	1760

Table 4.

Strength of building mortars based on dry building mixtures containing volcanic ash (on a dense structural base)

Portland cement, %	Quartz sand, %	Volcanic ash, %	CaO content in the product of 7-day hydration, %	Bending strength limit, MPa			Compressive strength, MPa		
				7 days	14 days	28 days	7 days	14 days	28 days
40	59	-	5,2	0,93	1,56	1,85	10,2	12,8	16,5
40	54	5	4,7	0,84	1,48	1,76	9,8	12,2	16,2
40	49	10	3,0	0,78	1,42	1,67	8,8	11,3	15,8
40	44	15	1,4	0,73	1,40	1,62	8,3	10,8	15,6
40	39	20	1,4	0,53	1,10	1,42	6,3	9,8	13,6

2. The effect of volcanic ash on the physical and mechanical properties of mixtures

The results of the study showed that replacing quartz sand with volcanic ash (VA) significantly affects a number of physical and mechanical properties of dry mixtures. As can be seen from Table 3, the following changes are observed with an increase in VA content:

- Changes in rheological properties: the setting time of the solution increases from 8 hours (VA 0%) to 12 hours (VA 20%), and plasticity increases from 8 cm to 9 cm. These changes are due to increased water demand (increase in normal density from 27% to 34%) due to the high dispersibility and surface area of VA. Increased water demand and prolonged setting time can improve the workability of the mortar during application.

- Reduction in density: Due to the lower specific weight and porous structure of VA compared to sand,

the density of the mortar is reduced from 1800 kg/m³ to 1760 kg/m³. This can be a positive factor in terms of obtaining lighter mixtures.

Mechanical strength development dynamics:

The effect of VA additive on strength is unstable. According to Table 4, in the initial stages of hardening (7 days), a decrease in strength is observed in both bending and compression. In particular, in a composition with 20% VA, the compressive strength after 7 days decreases sharply from 10.2 MPa to 6.3 MPa. This phenomenon is explained by the following factors:

1. A more porous microstructure formed as a result of increased water consumption by volcanic ash.

2. A slower rate of pozzolanic reaction compared to the initial hydration of cement.

However, the situation changes dramatically after 28 days of hardening. Although the compressive strength of compositions with 5% and 10% VA (16.2

MPa and 15.8 MPa, respectively) tends to decrease after 28 days, the strength of the composition with 15% VA (15.8 MPa) approaches the level of the composition without additives (16.5 MPa). This is due to the formation of additional C-S-H phases and the compaction of the microstructure as a result of the full development of pozzolanic reactions (Nikolaenko, 2014; Mechai et al., 2012). However, at 20% VA, a significant loss of strength (13.6 MPa) is still observed, confirming that it exceeds the optimum limit. Thus, at the optimum dosage (10-15%), the negative effect of VA on long-term strength is reduced.

3. The effect of volcanic ash on adhesion to various surfaces

The performance characteristics of building mortars are determined not only by their bulk properties, but also by their interaction with the substrate to which they are applied. The physical and chemical properties of the surface (porosity, texture, chemical nature) directly affect the strength of adhesion.

The next stage of our research examined the effect of VA on the strength of adhesion to surfaces of different chemical nature (concrete, ceramics, sawn stone). The results presented in Table 5 are very indicative in this regard.

Table 5.
Adhesion strength of building mortars with volcanic ash additives to various substrates after 28 days of hardening, MPa (GOST 28013, 1998)

Portland cement, %	Quartz sand, %	Volcanic ash, %	Adhesion, MPa								
			Concrete base			Ceramic brick base			Sawn stone		
			7 days	14 days	28 days	7 days	14 days	28 days	7 days	14 days	28 days
40	59	-	1,4	1,6	2,4	1,6	2,3	2,8	1,4	2,5	3,6
40	54	5	1,5	1,7	2,5	1,7	2,4	3,2	1,5	2,6	3,8
40	49	10	1,6	1,9	2,8	1,8	2,8	3,4	1,6	2,9	4,2
40	44	15	1,7	2,2	2,9	2,1	2,9	3,6	1,6	2,8	3,8
40	39	20	1,7	2,2	2,7	2,1	2,8	3,3	1,4	2,8	3,5

4. The effect of volcanic ash on adhesion and moisture-regulating properties

The data presented in Table 5 clearly show that an increase in the amount of volcanic ash (VA) systematically improves the adhesive strength of mortar with all the surfaces studied (concrete, ceramics, sawdust). This positive effect is explained by two main factors:

1. Physical and mechanical bonding: finely dispersed VA (mainly <0.08 mm), used instead of quartz sand (main fraction 0.1–0.63 mm), penetrates more effectively into the micro- and macro-pores of the base, which provides a larger contact area between the binder and the base and a stronger mechanical adhesion.

2. Chemical compatibility: High VA activity can lead to better chemical interaction not only with the main cement matrix, but also with the substrate surface, which improves adhesion.

The increase in adhesive strength is particularly noticeable on porous surfaces such as ceramics and sawn stone. On dense concrete surfaces, the increase is less pronounced but still noticeable due to limited penetration.

5. Sorption moisture and moisture-regulating capacity

One of the main objectives of the study was to develop dry building mixtures intended for use in conditions of high humidity. In this regard, the sorption moisture indicator, which characterises the material's ability to absorb moisture from the atmosphere, is of particular importance. This indicator was measured in accordance with GOST 24816-81 (1981) at a relative air humidity of 90%.

The results obtained (Table 6) indicate a positive effect of volcanic ash.

Table 6.
Sorption moisture content of hardened building mortars (GOST 24816-81, 1981)

Portlandcement, %	Quartz sand, %	Volcanic ash, %	Sorption humidity at 90% relative humidity, %
40	59	-	1,8
40	54	5	2,9
40	49	10	3,2
40	44	15	3,6
40	39	20	4,2

As can be seen from Table 6, adding 20% VA increases the sorption moisture content from 1.8% to 4.2%, i.e. more than twice. This is directly related to the high dispersibility and porous structure of VA, which increases its specific surface area and moisture capacity.

This quality makes the material particularly valuable for rooms that are constantly or periodically exposed to high humidity, such as basements, bathrooms

or attics. Such material can have a positive effect on the microclimate of a room, helping to absorb excess moisture and, as a result, reducing the risk of mould and mildew.

4. CONCLUSION

The study found that Molladag volcanic ash has high pozzolanic activity (79 mg CaO/g), which has a positive effect on the properties of dry cement-based building mixtures. Replacing 10-15% of quartz sand

with volcanic ash yielded optimal results. The compressive strength of these compositions after 28 days approached that of the control sample (16.5 MPa) and amounted to 15.6-15.8 MPa. Volcanic ash improved the rheological properties of the mortar, increasing the setting time to 11 hours and the plasticity to 9 cm. An increase in adhesive strength of 15-20% was observed, and the sorption moisture content more than doubled, reaching 3.6-4.2%. The results obtained indicate that Molladag volcanic ash is a promising local raw material source for the production of environmentally friendly and highly efficient dry construction mixtures intended for use in conditions of high humidity.

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